

Practical sensitivity-based optimization technique to solve the Hosting Capacity problem in unbalanced low voltage networks

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Abstract

This work addresses the problem of computing the hosting capacity of distributed energy resources, both generation and demand, in a three-phase four-wire low voltage network. A new methodology, based on the use of voltage and current sensitivities coefficients to model the system, allow to define a second-order cone programming formulation that granted the convexity of the problem. This approach results in a very practical and accurate tool capable of solving the hosting capacity problem in large unbalanced distribution networks, regardless of the initial operating conditions and the limiting constraints on voltages and currents. Tests on a large real low-voltage network demonstrate the practical usefulness of the tool, highlighting the accuracy of the results obtained.

Keywords: Hosting capacity, three-phase four-wire low voltage networks, voltage/current sensitivity coefficients, optimization-based solutions

Nomenclature

Throughout this work, the following notation is used:

i, j, k	Indexes for buses
$q, m \in \{a, b, c\}$	Indexes for phases
$p, h \in \{a, b, c, n\}$	Indexes for phases including neutral
$U_i^p = e_i^p + j f_i^p$	Phase p to ground complex voltage at bus i
V_i^p	Phase p to ground voltage magnitude at bus i ,
$\hat{U}_i^q = \hat{e}_i^q + j \hat{f}_i^q$	Phase q to neutral complex voltage at bus i
\hat{V}_i^q	Phase q to neutral voltage magnitude at bus i ,
$G_i^p = c_i^p + j d_i^p$	Phase p complex current injection at bus i
$G_{ij}^p = c_{ij}^p + j d_{ij}^p$	Phase p complex current from i to j through branch ij
I_{ij}^p	Phase p current magnitude through branch ij ,
$Y_{ij}^{ph} = G_{ij}^{ph} + j B_{ij}^{ph}$	element of nodal admittance matrix
$z_{ij}^{ph} = r_{ij}^{ph} + j x_{ij}^{ph}$	element of the series impedance matrix of branch ij
$S_i^q = P_i^q + j Q_i^q$	phase q complex power injected at bus i
$N + 1$	number of buses in the network
B	number of branches in the network.

In the following, lowercase bold letters denote vectors, and uppercase bold letters represent matrices.

1. Introduction

The global energy transition is driving a rapid increase in the integration of Distributed Energy Resources (DERs), particularly rooftop solar photovoltaic (PV) systems, into low-voltage (LV) distribution networks. Although DERs offer numerous benefits, including reduced carbon emissions and increased customer participation, their intermittent and uncontrolled nature poses significant challenges to the reliable and safe operation of distribution grids, such as rise and fluctuation voltages, thermal overload of network components, and potential issues with protection coordination [1, 2]. To manage these challenges, the concept of Hosting Capacity (HC) has emerged as a crucial tool. HC quantifies the maximum amount of DER that a distribution network can accommodate without requiring costly infrastructure upgrades or compromising power quality and reliability [3]. Accurate and efficient HC assessment is therefore essential for distribution system operators (DSOs) to facilitate the continued growth of DERs while maintaining grid integrity [4].

Existing methodologies for assessing the HC of distribution networks can be broadly categorized into four main approaches: deterministic, stochastic, optimization-based, and streamlined methods [5]. Deterministic approaches rely on fixed input parameters and power flow analysis to determine the maximum DER capacity that can be accommodated without violating pre-defined network constraints. Basic Deterministic Methods often utilize simplified rules of thumb, such as limiting DER capacity to a percentage of peak load or transformer rating, but these can be overly conservative and do not capture the specific characteristics of individual feeders [1]. Feeder-Based Approaches improve upon this by considering specific feeder characteristics to provide more refined HC estimates [5]. Nomogram-Based Approaches take this a step further by developing graphical tools (nomograms) that allow for quick and visual HC estimation based on key feeder parameters. For instance, in [6] a feeder-based deterministic approach is extended to create a nomogram for simplified HC assessment, particularly useful for utilities. Analytical optimal power flow (OPF) methods have been also used for the assessment of HC, where analytical expressions and optimization methods are used to model the problem [7]. [8] provides a multi-stage algorithm for maximizing DER capacity, featuring an initial analytical stage to determine optimal DER locations, and a subsequent OPF stage to refine capacity estimates. A common drawback across all the cited references is their inherent conservatism.

Stochastic approaches to the HC problem directly address the uncertainties inherent in DER integration, such as fluctuating generation, variable loads, and unknown DER locations. These methods typically employ probabilistic models and Monte Carlo simulations to capture a wide range of operating scenarios. For instance, [9] introduces a probabilistic planning method, utilizing Monte Carlo simulations to estimate the probability of voltage violations, thereby moving beyond deterministic worst-case assumptions. Similarly, [10] uses a multi-objective optimization approach combined with Monte Carlo simulations to maximize DER HC while minimizing power losses. Finally, [3] extended existing deterministic approaches by employing probabilistic models to the three-phase unbalanced feeders. Although these approaches are less conservative for the assessment of HC compared to deterministic approaches, the computational complexity increases, as a large number of simulations may be required to achieve statistically significant results.

Optimization-based approaches formulate the problem as a mathemat-

ical optimization, with the aim of maximizing DER integration while satisfying operational constraints. Depending on the aim of the optimization problem they can be classified in Single-Objective or Multi-Objective Optimization. For example, in [10] a multi-objective optimization framework is stated to balance DER HC with power loss minimization. To address the non-convexity of the AC power flow equations some works develop Convex Inner Approximations (CIA), such as those proposed in [3] and [2]. This fact enables the use of efficient convex optimization solvers while still guaranteeing the feasibility of the solution. Robust Optimization techniques, further explored in [2], explicitly account for uncertainties in DER output, load variations, or network parameters, by finding solutions that remain feasible under a range of possible scenarios. Optimization-based approaches often require significant computational effort, particularly for large-scale networks. The need for accurate network models and the potential for simplifying assumptions to improve tractability can also be limiting factors.

Beyond the traditional model-based methods, recent research has explored alternative approaches for HC assessment. Data-Driven Approaches leverage the increasing availability of smart meter data and other sensor measurements to estimate HC without relying on detailed network models. These methods often employ machine learning techniques, such as regression models, to learn the relationship between power injections, voltage magnitudes, and other relevant variables. [11] presents a privacy-preserving approach using a conditional parametric model, based on varying coefficient linear regression, to estimate sensitivity factors from smart meter data. The accuracy and reliability of these kind of methods depend heavily on the quality and quantity of available data, and they may not always provide guarantees of feasibility.

Other modern alternatives to the HC problem are the Hybrid Approaches that combine elements of different methodologies, such as deterministic and stochastic, or optimization-based and data-driven to capitalize the complementary strengths.

This work presents a novel approach to address the HC problem on LV distribution networks. The main contributions are:

- Sensitivity-Based Convex Optimization Framework: The proposed methodology uses voltage and current sensitivities derived from the network model to almost completely linearize the HC problem. This results in a Second-Order Cone Programming (SOCP) formulation that

can be efficiently solved under various load and generation scenarios, ensuring both accuracy and computational efficiency.

- **Modeling and Management of Unbalanced LV Networks:** The approach explicitly accounts for unbalanced conditions in three-phase four-wire (3P-4W) LV networks, where single-phase modeling is insufficient. By evaluating each phase and its interactions with the rest of conductors, the method ensures accurate constraint enforcement and realistic representation of real-world network behavior.

The rest of the work is organized as follows. Section 2 describes and formulates the hosting capacity problem addressed in this study. Section 3 introduces the detailed network model and the approximations used. Section 4 details the proposed solution methodology, while Section 5 presents the simulation results. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 6.

2. Hosting capacity problem

The hosting capacity problem addressed in this work follows its deterministic definition as presented in previous studies [12, 13]. Specifically, it refers to the maximum amount of new resources that a power network can accommodate without violating operational limits or compromising safety constraints. The resources may include distributed generation units as well as controllable or non-controllable loads, depending on the context and configuration of the network.

In this work, the hosting capacity problem is formulated for low-voltage distribution networks. These networks are typically characterized by unbalanced conditions, primarily arising from asymmetrical line configurations and uneven distributions of single-phase loads. The increasing integration of distributed photovoltaic generation and the widespread deployment of electric vehicle charging stations are introducing new operational challenges in such networks. These changes can significantly affect voltage profiles, line loading, and overall network stability, making it essential to accurately assess the maximum amount of additional resources that the network can host without violating operational constraints.

The exact HC optimization problem (EHCOP) that addresses the hosting capacity problem consists in determining the values of the input variables \mathbf{u} (in this case, representing the active power injections at the network buses)

that minimize the objective function $f(\mathbf{u})$, which quantifies the hosting capacity of the network. Active power injections, defined as input signals \mathbf{u} , determine the network outputs through the relationship $\mathbf{y} = h(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{w})$ (nodal voltages and line currents). The function h represents the network constraints derived from Kirchhoff laws and the models of power components (lines, transformers, loads, generators, etc.). \mathbf{w} takes into account uncontrollable factors, such as existing load demand or fixed generation units. Finally, both input and output signals are constrained to remain within operational limits, as enforced by the inequality constraints $g(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{y}) \leq 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\mathbf{u}} \quad & f(\mathbf{u}), \\ & y = h(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{w}), \\ & g(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{y}) \leq 0. \end{aligned}$$

The main drawback of this EHCOP lies in its highly nonlinear and non-convex nature, which leads to several critical limitations:

- There is no guarantee that a feasible solution exists.
- Any solution found may correspond to a local rather than a global optimum.
- Solving the problem demands significant computational effort, especially for networks of realistic size.

In addition, the hosting capacity problem must be evaluated under various initial load and generation scenarios. This implies that the EHCOP needs to be solved independently for each scenario, substantially increasing the overall computational burden of the analysis.

The aim of this work is to address the computational challenges associated with the EHCOP by proposing an approximation based on convex relaxation. The approach leverages sensitivity analysis to reformulate the original problem into a convex optimization framework, significantly reducing the computational effort required for its solution. It will be demonstrated that the errors introduced by this simplification are minimal and, in most practical cases, negligible, thereby preserving the accuracy of the hosting capacity assessment while enabling efficient large-scale evaluations.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of a distribution network bus highlighting node voltages and node injected currents.

3. Modeling Framework and Sensitivity-Based Approximations

This section first presents the mathematical formulation of the low-voltage distribution network model used to assess the proposed problem. Following the model derivation, a sensitivity analysis is carried out to evaluate how variations in active power injections influence key output variables, namely, nodal voltages and line currents. The resulting sensitivities are then employed to reformulate the exact optimization problem (EHCOP) described in the previous section, enabling a more computationally efficient approximation based on convex relaxation techniques.

3.1. Distribution network modeling

The low-voltage networks under study are three-phase four-wire systems characterized by an asymmetrical configuration of their conductors and an unbalanced demand/generation of the consumers/generators connected to them. This means that a single-phase equivalent model of the network cannot be used; instead, a detailed model must be developed that includes information from all four conductors and their interactions.

The network model is formulated in terms of nodal voltages (voltages relative to ground potential) and current injections, variables specified in Fig. 1, which depicts a generic bus i consisting of four nodes: three phases (a , b , and c) and the neutral (n). Bus i is connected to other buses through series elements such as overhead or underground lines and transformers. Loads and distributed generators are connected among phases a , b , or/and c and the neutral n at each bus i , modeling power consumption and generation, respectively. The possible ground connection of the neutral at bus i is modeled by a resistor R_i^g . Thus, the equations that describe the power flows in the network are given by the nodal equations (1)¹, together with the boundary constraints defined in (2) and (3) corresponding to the usual constant power model assumed for loads and generators:

$$\sum_{j=1}^N \sum_h \mathcal{Y}_{ij}^{ph} \mathcal{U}_j^h - \mathcal{G}_i^p = 0, \quad \forall p \in \{a, b, c, n\}, \forall i = 1, \dots, N, \quad (1)$$

$$\mathcal{S}_i^q - (\mathcal{U}_i^q - \mathcal{U}_i^n) \mathcal{G}_i^{q*} = 0, \quad \forall q \in \{a, b, c\}, \forall i = 1, \dots, N, \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_p \mathcal{G}_i^p = 0, \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, N, \quad (3)$$

where $\mathcal{S}_i^q = \mathcal{S}_{g,i}^q - \mathcal{S}_{d,i}^q$, with subscripts d and g denoting demand and generation, respectively.

Note that this formulation ensures that any network component is modeled through its nodal admittance matrix: transformers with any connection among windings, any power lines no matter their configuration (overhead or underground) or the number of phases (three-phase four-wire, three-phase three-wire, two-phase three-wire, etc.) and shunt elements [14]. Likewise, the connectivity between components is reflected in this node admittance matrix, allowing both radial and meshed networks to be modeled.

3.2. Network model approximations

The sensitivities of the problem outputs, phase node voltages and branch currents, with respect to the inputs (specifically, the active power injections) are deduced based on the formulation and solution of the power flow problem for the network. This process relies on the precise network model (1)–(3), which allows expressing the whole network model in terms of voltage and

¹The slack bus is assumed to be bus $N+1$

current variables. While traditional approaches formulate the power flow using only the real and imaginary parts of the nodal voltages as state variables, that is, eliminating currents by combining equations (1) and (2); this work also includes the real and imaginary parts of the current injections as explicit variables. This extended formulation has been proved to improve the convergence characteristics of the power flow solver [15]. To compute the system's response under a given load and generation scenario $\mathcal{S}_{d,i}^q|_0$, $\mathcal{S}_{g,i}^q|_0$, Newton's method is applied iteratively, yielding the corresponding operating point defined by $\mathcal{G}_i^p|_0$ and $\mathcal{U}_i^p|_0$, as detailed in [15]. The linearization of the power flow equations around this operating point results in a model of the form described by (4), from which the desired input-output sensitivities can be extracted:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Y} & -\mathbf{U}_{8N} \\ \mathbf{DI}|_0 & \mathbf{DV}|_0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{V} \\ \Delta \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \Delta \mathbf{S} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

The Appendix details all the matrices and vectors of (4). Here, $\Delta \mathbf{V}$ and $\Delta \mathbf{I}$ denote vectors containing all the nodal voltage deviations $\Delta \mathbf{V}_i = [\Delta \mathbf{e}_i \ \Delta \mathbf{f}_i]^T$ and current deviations $\Delta \mathbf{I}_i = [\Delta \mathbf{c}_i \ \Delta \mathbf{d}_i]^T$, respectively, for each bus i ; $\Delta \mathbf{S}$ represents the vector of power mismatch terms $\Delta \mathbf{S}_i = [\Delta \mathbf{P}_i \ \Delta \mathbf{Q}_i]^T$ across all buses. The matrix \mathbf{Y} is the system admittance matrix, whose sub-blocks \mathbf{Y}_{ij} are defined in (A-1) of the Appendix. The term \mathbf{U}_{8N} denotes the identity matrix of size $8N \times 8N$. Finally, $\mathbf{DI}|_0$ and $\mathbf{DV}|_0$ are block-diagonal matrices constructed from the current- and voltage-related blocks appearing on the left-hand side of (A-2) in the Appendix that are denoted by $\mathbf{DI}_i|_0$ and $\mathbf{DV}_i|_0$, respectively. For a more detailed explanation reader is referred to [15].

The following subsections demonstrate how the sensitivities $\partial \mathbf{y} / \partial \mathbf{u}$, representing the variation of any system output in \mathbf{y} with respect to any input signal in \mathbf{u} , can be derived from (4). These sensitivities enable the computation of the new system state in a linearized manner, as expressed in (5):

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{y}_0 + \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \mathbf{u}} \right|_0 \Delta \mathbf{u}, \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{y}_0 denotes the vector composed of the values of the output variables at the initial operating point, and $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ represents the deviation in active power injection at every bus in the network. Note that (5) is an approximation of function h in the EHCOP. As long as the variations in the input signals are not excessively large, the updated state computed using this linear approx-

imation (5) remains close to the exact solution obtained by solving the full nonlinear power flow equations (1)–(3) via Newton’s method. This accuracy will be demonstrated in Section 5 of results.

3.2.1. Nodal Voltage Sensitivities

A method to obtain the sensitivity coefficients consists of using the second row of system (4) to eliminate $\Delta \mathbf{I}$ from the first row, resulting in:

$$(\mathbf{Y} + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{V}|_0^{-1}\mathbf{D}\mathbf{I}|_0) \Delta \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{D}\mathbf{V}|_0^{-1}\Delta \mathbf{S}. \quad (6)$$

Now, it is straightforward to obtain the voltage sensitivities at each node with respect to the power injections, as defined in (7):

$$\frac{\Delta \mathbf{V}}{\Delta \mathbf{S}} = (\mathbf{Y} + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{V}|_0^{-1}\mathbf{D}\mathbf{I}|_0)^{-1} \mathbf{D}\mathbf{V}|_0^{-1}. \quad (7)$$

Note that since rectangular coordinates are used, equation (7) defines, for every bus i , an $8 \times 8N$ matrix in which the sensitivities of the real and imaginary parts of voltages of the four phases with respect to active and reactive power injections at every bus and phase of the network are obtained. Specifically, these include $\partial e_i^p / \partial P_k^q$, $\partial e_i^p / \partial Q_k^q$, $\partial f_i^p / \partial P_k^q$, and $\partial f_i^p / \partial Q_k^q$ for every combination of $p \in \{a, b, c, n\}$, $q \in \{a, b, c\}$ and every pair of nodes i, k . In the proposed approach, only active power injections are considered as variables; therefore, the sensitivities with respect to reactive power injections are omitted. However, extending the formulation to include reactive power injections is straightforward from this point.

In the problem addressed, the sensitivities of voltage magnitude with respect to input signals are of interest, as the hosting capacity problem is constrained by voltage operational limits. It is important to distinguish between phase-to-ground voltages \mathbf{u}_i and phase-to-neutral voltages $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_i$, being voltage operational limits usually imposed on phase-to-neutral voltage magnitudes \hat{V}_i . Phase-to-neutral voltages represent the voltages across each phase of the consumers or generators connected to the network and are obtained from the phase-to-ground voltages by simple subtraction, i.e., $\hat{u}_i^q = u_i^q - u_i^n$. Once the phase-to-ground voltage sensitivities have been computed using (7), the phase-to-neutral voltage sensitivities $\frac{\Delta \hat{\mathbf{V}}}{\Delta \mathbf{S}}$ can be readily obtained by applying the aforementioned difference. Next, an expression to obtain the sensitivities of phase-to-neutral voltage magnitudes \hat{V}_i can be derived by applying a first-order Taylor series expansion to the expression $\hat{V}_i^p = \sqrt{(\hat{e}_i^p)^2 + (\hat{f}_i^p)^2}$

and employing the chain rule. This leads to the computation of the desired sensitivities, as shown in (8):

$$\frac{\partial \hat{V}_i^q}{\partial P_k^q} = \frac{\hat{e}_i^q}{\hat{V}_i^q} \frac{\partial \hat{e}_i^q}{\partial P_k^q} + \frac{\hat{f}_i^q}{\hat{V}_i^q} \frac{\partial \hat{f}_i^q}{\partial P_k^q}, \quad (8)$$

where $\hat{e}_i^q = e_i^q - e_i^n$, $\hat{f}_i^q = f_i^q - f_i^n$, $\partial \hat{e}_i^q / \partial P_k^q = \partial e_i^q / \partial P_k^q - \partial e_i^n / \partial P_k^q$, and $\partial \hat{f}_i^q / \partial P_k^q = \partial f_i^q / \partial P_k^q - \partial f_i^n / \partial P_k^q$ for $q \in \{a, b, c\}$.

3.3. Line Current Sensitivities

Line current sensitivities can be computed once the nodal voltage sensitivities have been obtained, by taking into account the line impedance and applying Ohm's law. Specifically, for a three-phase four-wire line connecting buses i and j , and characterized by an admittance matrix \mathbf{y}_{ij} , the line current sensitivities are obtained by applying (9) and using the nodal voltage sensitivities computed via (7).

$$\frac{\Delta \mathbf{I}_{ij}}{\Delta \mathbf{S}} = \mathbf{Z}_{ij}^{-1} \left(\frac{\Delta \mathbf{V}_i}{\Delta \mathbf{S}} - \frac{\Delta \mathbf{V}_j}{\Delta \mathbf{S}} \right). \quad (9)$$

As previously mentioned, voltage magnitude sensitivities are essential in this study due to the constraints imposed by operational voltage limits. Similarly, for line current magnitudes, it is necessary to consider their sensitivities with respect to input variables since they are constrained by thermal ampacity limits in power lines. As with voltages, these current magnitude sensitivities can be approximated using a first-order Taylor expansion and the chain rule:

$$\frac{\partial I_{ij}^p}{\partial P_k^q} = \frac{c_{ij}^p}{I_{ij}^p} \frac{\partial c_{ij}^p}{\partial P_k^q} + \frac{d_{ij}^p}{I_{ij}^p} \frac{\partial d_{ij}^p}{\partial P_k^q}. \quad (10)$$

However, this linear approximation has been found to be somewhat inaccurate for current magnitudes, as second-order terms play a more significant role in their behavior [16]. Therefore, when higher accuracy is required, current magnitudes are computed directly from their definition (11), at the cost of slightly increasing the computational effort:

$$I_{ij}^p = \sqrt{\left(c_{ij|_0}^p + \Delta c_{ij}^p \right)^2 + \left(d_{ij|_0}^p + \Delta d_{ij}^p \right)^2}, \quad (11)$$

where the updated real and imaginary components of the current are obtained using the sensitivity factors from (9), such that:

$$\mathcal{G}_{ij}^p = \mathcal{G}_{ij}^p|_0 + \Delta\mathcal{G}_{ij}^p = \left(c_{ij}^p|_0 + j \cdot d_{ij}^p|_0 \right) + \left(\Delta c_{ij}^p + j \cdot \Delta d_{ij}^p \right).$$

This approach ensures greater accuracy in computing current magnitudes, particularly under conditions where nonlinear effects cannot be neglected.

4. Sensitivity-based HC optimization problem

This section proposes a solution to the hosting capacity problem based on the models developed in Section 3. The approach derives a Simplified HC Optimization Program (SHCOP) from the Exact Optimization Problem (EHCOP), using the linear approximations detailed in previous sections. The formulation focuses on determining the maximum amount of distributed resources that can be accommodated at each bus and phase of the network without violating operational constraints. The extension to the case of additional load is straightforward and this work presents results for both scenarios in the numerical validation section. The formulation of the problem is specified in (12):

$$\max \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{q \in \{a,b,c\}} \Delta P_i^q \quad (12a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \hat{V}_i^q = \hat{V}_i^q|_0 + \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{q \in \{a,b,c\}} \left. \frac{\partial \hat{V}_i^q}{\partial P_j^q} \right|_0 \Delta P_j^q, \quad \begin{array}{l} \forall i = 1, \dots, N \\ \forall q = a, b, c \end{array} \quad (12b)$$

$$c_{ij}^p = c_{ij}^p|_0 + \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{q \in \{a,b,c\}} \left. \frac{\partial c_{ij}^p}{\partial P_k^q} \right|_0 \Delta P_k^q, \quad \begin{array}{l} \forall ij = 1, \dots, B \\ \forall p = a, b, c, n \end{array} \quad (12c)$$

$$d_{ij}^p = d_{ij}^p|_0 + \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{q \in \{a,b,c\}} \left. \frac{\partial d_{ij}^p}{\partial P_k^q} \right|_0 \Delta P_k^q, \quad \begin{array}{l} \forall ij = 1, \dots, B \\ \forall p = a, b, c, n \end{array} \quad (12d)$$

$$\hat{V}_{min} \leq \hat{V}_i^q \leq \hat{V}_{max}, \quad \begin{array}{l} \forall i = 1, \dots, N \\ \forall q = a, b, c \end{array} \quad (12e)$$

$$0 \leq (c_{ij}^p)^2 + (d_{ij}^p)^2 \leq I_{ij,max}^2, \quad \begin{array}{l} \forall ij = 1, \dots, B \\ \forall p = a, b, c, n \end{array} \quad (12f)$$

$$0 \leq \Delta P_i^q \leq \Delta P_{i,max}, \quad \begin{array}{l} \forall i = 1, \dots, N \\ \forall q = a, b, c \end{array} \quad (12g)$$

The set of constraints includes the linearized expressions for voltage magnitudes and current components obtained from the first-order Taylor expansion around an initial operating point. Specifically, constraint (12b) defines the relationship between voltage magnitude deviations and active power injections through precomputed sensitivity factors. Similarly, the real and imaginary parts of the branch currents are modeled using their linear approximations in (12c) and (12d), respectively. Operational limits are enforced to ensure system security: constraint (12e) bounds the post-injection voltage magnitudes within acceptable ranges, while (12f) ensures that line current magnitudes remain below thermal limits. Finally, constraint (12g) restricts the maximum allowable power injection per bus and phase, reflecting physical or contractual limitations of the new resources being integrated.

Although the proposed optimization problem is not entirely linear, the only nonlinear constraint is the second-order cone constraint (12f), which is convex. As a result, the overall problem becomes a convex Second-Order Cone Program (SOCP). This represents a significant improvement over the original Exact Optimization Problem, which is nonlinear and nonconvex. By leveraging linear approximations around the operating point and preserving convexity in the only nonlinear constraint, we obtain a computationally efficient and reliable convex formulation.

Fig. 2 illustrates the overall methodology implemented to compute the hosting capacity problem in unbalanced low-voltage networks. This approach can be applied to assess both generation and demand hosting capacity. Next, each main step of this procedure is described in detail:

- (Step 1) Define a base case including the network model and representative load and generation profiles to serve as the initial operating point for hosting capacity assessment.
- (Step 2) Perform a power flow analysis to determine the complete operating initial state of the network.
- (Step 3) Compute the sensitivity coefficients used to linearize the network equations, which are then incorporated as constraints in the SHCOP.
- (Step 4) Solve the SHCOP to determine the maximum additional generation or demand that can be accommodated at each node and phase without violating operational constraints.

Figure 2: Hosting capacity methodology flow chart

- (Step 5) Apply the obtained solution to the base case and solve the power flow problem using the detailed network model to determine the actual operating state achieved.
- (Step 6) If the operating state computed in Step 5 violates any operational limits, update the sensitivity coefficients and repeat the process. Otherwise, the solution is valid and the procedure ends.

5. Performance assessment

This section evaluates the performance of the proposed methodology for computing hosting capacity in low-voltage distribution networks. The simulations are carried out on a detailed unbalanced LV network, which serves as the base case for assessing both generation and demand hosting capacity. First, the maximum additional distributed generation that can be integrated without violating operational constraints is determined. Subsequently, the same methodology is applied to evaluate the capability of the network to accommodate new load demands, demonstrating the versatility and effectiveness of the approach. Moreover, the HC problem is solved in both cases

under different voltage conditions on the reference bus.

5.1. Description of the Low Voltage Test System

To evaluate the proposed hosting capacity methodology, a test case has been developed based on an adapted version of the low-voltage networks from northern Spain, originally described and thoroughly documented in [17]. These distribution systems consist of 22 independent radial LV networks, each supplied by a 22/0.42 kV secondary substation located at the head of the network. For further details on the network topologies, line parameters, and load characteristics, the reader is referred to [17] and the publicly available repository [18].

One of these radial networks, the largest one, has been selected and modified to represent a scenario with moderate penetration of distributed renewable generation (referred to as the “65019 generation case”). A single-line diagram of this network, including labels for each of the feeders, is shown in Fig. 3, where orange buses indicate load connection points and blue buses represent non-load nodes. Additional descriptive details of the network are summarized in Table 1. The system comprises 148 buses, most of them with all three phases and neutral and the fewest with only a single phase and neutral, resulting in 592 nodes.

Table 1: Main figures of the test network

Feature	Value
Transformer rated power (kVA)	630
Extent (km)	2.2
Number of feeders	6
Number of loads	459
Number of buses	148
Number of nodes	592
Total Load (kVA)	48.08
Total Generation (kW)	2.2

In the proposed methodology, identifying candidate nodes that can host new generation or demand is essential, as these nodes will be associated with control variables in the SHCOP formulation. In the test network, all buses with at least one phase connected to a load are considered candidates, i.e., 444 nodes out of the total 592. The maximum hosting capacity for each

Figure 3: Low Voltage Network 65019 used to test the methodology.

phase q and bus i , denoted as $\Delta P_{i,max}^q$, is set to the aggregated contracted power of the loads at that bus and phase, which moves in a range from 3 to 6 kW. Voltage limits are defined according to regulatory standards, with allowable deviations of $\pm 7\%$ of the nominal voltage. Thermal limits are set such that the current in each network segment must not exceed 100% of the maximum current rating specified by the cable type.

5.2. Evaluation of Generation Hosting Capacity

Starting from the base case and following the proposed methodology, the approach has been applied to compute the generation hosting capacity. This represents the maximum amount of new distributed generation that the network can accommodate without violating operational constraints. The results are summarized in Table 2, which reports the hosting capacity per phase and low-voltage feeder. The total hosting capacity amounts to 232.1 kW, approximately 37% with respect to the rated power of the transformer, and its spatial distribution across the network is illustrated in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Generation hosting capacity distribution along the single-line diagram

Table 2: Calculated Generation Hosting Capacity per phase and low voltage feeder in kW. Slack voltage 1.04 p.u.

Feeder	Phase a	Phase b	Phase c	Total
1	5.4	2.8	8.5	16.7
2	14.1	3.4	8.0	25.5
3	5.2	3.0	16.9	25.1
4	3.1	17.9	16.5	37.5
5	47.9	37.9	16.3	102.1
6	7.0	10.4	7.8	25.2

These results were obtained in a single iteration of the proposed methodology schemed in Fig. 2, i.e., the resulting solution after solving (12), when applied to the base case and followed by a power flow analysis, was found to comply with all defined operational limits, as shown in Table 3. This table presents the maximum phase-to-neutral voltages (\hat{V}_{max}) and the maximum line loading (Ld_{max}), calculated as the ratio of the current flowing through the conductor with respect to the maximum ampacity of the line, under three

different operating conditions:

1. Base Case: Corresponds to the initial operating scenario used as the starting point for calculating the hosting capacity.
2. SHCOP: Refers to the voltage and loading conditions obtained after solving the Simplified Optimization Problem (SHCOP).
3. Final state: Represents the voltage and loading conditions obtained by applying the hosting capacity solution from the SHCOP to the base case and solving the power flow using the detailed network model.

Table 3: Maximum Node Voltages and Line Load Congestion Before and After Hosting Capacity Integration. Slack voltage 1.04 p.u.

Parameter	Base case	SHCOP	Final state
\hat{V}_{\max}^a (pu)	1.0392	1.0516	1.0517
\hat{V}_{\max}^b (pu)	1.0394	1.0518	1.0519
\hat{V}_{\max}^c (pu)	1.0398	1.0453	1.0454
Ld_{\max}^a (%)	41.05	97.23	99.58
Ld_{\max}^b (%)	27.83	97.71	99.40
Ld_{\max}^c (%)	12.16	98.62	99.23

As shown in Table 3, the results are primarily constrained by the load congestion limits. These limits are nearly reached in all phases after applying the hosting capacity solution. Meanwhile, the nodal voltages increase due to the additional power injections but remain within the allowable voltage band and far from the upper regulatory limit. Fig. 5, Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 illustrate the nodal voltages and branch loading reached in the Base Case (a) and after applying generation hosting capacity (b) for each phase using a single line diagram. As it can be seen in (b) representations, the main loading restrictions that limits generation hosting capacity is located in Feeder 5. In addition, it is observed that, in general, the nodal voltages are increased in the three phases as a consequence of the increase in the injection to the grid as expected. However, in the case of phase a, Feeder 2 shows a slight reduction in its voltages due to the load imbalance of the network.

In addition, it is worth pointing out that the voltages and congestion levels calculated through the power flow analysis are very close to those obtained using the sensitivity coefficients as solution of the SHCOP. This

consistency confirms the reliability of the proposed linearized approach and supports its use in accurately estimating the network operating conditions. This conclusion is especially significant for the tested case, since the sensitivity coefficients are computed once for a starting scenario with only 2.2 kW of distributed generation, while the final PV penetration grows until 232.1 kW, more than 10 times the initial one.

Finally, the results presented in Table 3, and in Fig. 5, Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, were calculated by imposing a balanced voltage at reference bus of 1.04 pu, a value above the nominal voltage that is commonly targeted in distribution networks in order to minimize losses. To validate the applicability of the proposed method for calculating generation hosting capacity, a second test is performed considering the same load and generation starting scenario but under an even greater reference voltage, seeking to activate voltage limits instead of capacity limits when solving (12). So, for a voltage level of $1.07 \cdot V_{\text{rated}}$ (pu) at the head of the network, the new resulting network's generation hosting capacity is significantly lower than in the previous first test, 12.3 kW, what is expected taking into account the high starting operating voltages, quite close to the upper limit.

Table 4: Generation hosting capacity in alternative reference voltage scenario: slack voltage 1.07 p.u.

Parameter	Base case	Final state
\hat{V}_{\max}^a (pu)	1.07	1.07
\hat{V}_{\max}^b (pu)	1.07	1.07
\hat{V}_{\max}^c (pu)	1.07	1.07
\hat{V}_{\min}^a (pu)	1.0664	1.0682
\hat{V}_{\min}^b (pu)	1.0685	1.0688
\hat{V}_{\min}^c (pu)	1.0692	1.0698
Ld_{\max}^a (%)	38.44	27.63
Ld_{\max}^b (%)	26.03	21.09
Ld_{\max}^c (%)	11.37	12.16

Table 4 shows the maximum and minimum voltages, as well as the maximum congestion, per phase, for both the base case and the new final scenario. It can be observed that, unlike in the previous case, the limitation to the hosting capacity is imposed by the maximum voltage levels. This can be seen by observing the minimum voltages, clearly showing that the optimal hosting

capacity calculated brings both the minimum and maximum voltage values very close to their respective limits, effectively maximizing the amount of new generation that the network can accommodate. Once again, these results are obtained in a single iteration of the proposed whole methodology, what shows that the sensitivities-based solution is very accurate.

Figure 5: Graphical Representation of Maximum Node Voltages and Line Load Congestion Before (a) and After Applying the Calculated Generation (b) and Demand Hosting Capacity (c) in Phase a

Figure 6: Graphical Representation of Maximum Node Voltages and Line Load Congestion Before (a) and After Applying the Calculated Generation (b) and Demand Hosting Capacity (c) in Phase b

Figure 7: Graphical Representation of Maximum Node Voltages and Line Load Congestion Before (a) and After Applying the Calculated Generation (b) and Demand Hosting Capacity (c) in Phase c

Figure 8: Demand hosting capacity distribution along the single-line diagram

5.3. Evaluation of Demand Hosting Capacity

Similar to the generation hosting capacity case, Table 5 presents the results for demand hosting capacity. This indicates the additional load that the network can accommodate, reported per phase and feeder. The total capacity amounts to 132.4 kW, approximately 21 % with respect to the rated power of the transformer. The solution is mainly constrained by thermal limits, while the resulting voltage levels remain above the minimum operational thresholds. The spatial distribution of this capacity is shown in Fig. 8.

Table 5: Calculated Demand Hosting Capacity per phase and low voltage feeder in kW. Slack voltage 1.04 p.u.

Feeder	Phase a	Phase b	Phase c	Total
1	4.9	0.8	0.5	6.2
2	3.6	1.8	4.8	10.2
3	2.1	1.6	7.9	11.6
4	2.3	6.5	15.2	24.0
5	15.9	18.4	10.9	45.2
6	7.0	14.6	13.6	35.2

Additionally, Table 6 presents the minimum nodal voltages and maximum line congestions for each phase, under the same three operating conditions as in the generation case. It can be observed that the loading levels approach the defined thermal limits, while the minimum voltages, although reduced due to the additional demand, remain above the lower operational thresholds. The small difference between the power flow results and those obtained using the sensitivity coefficients further supports the accuracy and validity of the linearized approach.

Table 6: Minimum Node Voltages and Maximum Line Load Congestion Before and After Demand Hosting Capacity Integration. Slack voltage 1.04 p.u.

Parameter	Base case	SHCOP	Final state
\hat{V}_{\min}^a (pu)	1.0359	1.0347	1.0347
\hat{V}_{\min}^b (pu)	1.0381	1.0238	1.0240
\hat{V}_{\min}^c (pu)	1.0389	1.0249	1.0247
Ld_{\max}^a (%)	41.05	99.46	98.58
Ld_{\max}^b (%)	27.83	99.98	99.14
Ld_{\max}^c (%)	12.16	99.91	99.58

Similarly to the previous case, Fig. 5, Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 illustrate the nodal voltages and branch loading reached in the Base Case (a) and after applying demand hosting capacity (c) for each phase using a single line diagram. As it can be seen in (c) representations, the main loading restrictions that limits generation hosting capacity is located in the phase c of Feeder 2 . In the case of demand, in contrast to the generation, and as expected, nodal voltages decrease in the three phases as a consequence of the increase grid demand.

For the case of demand hosting capacity, a second test has also been carried out considering an alternative slack voltage as in the previous subsection. Table 7 presents the new results when a lower reference voltage is defined, specifically $0.94 \cdot V_{\text{rated}}$ (pu). This case may be representative of power transformers located close to primary substations with a very high tap position, or low-voltage networks with high demand. Demand hosting capacity is lower than in the previous scenario, totaling 116 kW.

Table 7: Demand hosting capacity in alternative reference voltage scenario: slack voltage 0.94 p.u.

Parameter	Base case	Final state
\hat{V}_{\max}^a (pu)	0.94	0.939
\hat{V}_{\max}^b (pu)	0.94	0.939
\hat{V}_{\max}^c (pu)	0.94	0.939
\hat{V}_{\min}^a (pu)	0.936	0.936
\hat{V}_{\min}^b (pu)	0.9385	0.9351
\hat{V}_{\min}^c (pu)	0.939	0.931
Ld_{\max}^a (%)	43.78	99.95
Ld_{\max}^b (%)	29.64	99.98
Ld_{\max}^c (%)	12.94	99.92

The results shown in Table 7 highlight that the proposed methodology has successfully converged to a hosting capacity value that brings both the voltage levels and branch loading very close to their respective limits.

Comparing these last results of Table 7, calculated under restrictive voltage conditions in the reference bus, with those obtained in scenarios where voltages are centered between the upper and lower limits, Table 6, it is possible to identify the specific needs of low-voltage networks to accommodate new demand capacity. Indeed, in this particular case, it can be inferred that the main limitation of the system to accommodate new demand lies in the maximum capacity of the cables and not in voltage issues.

It is also worth mentioning that, once again, the whole proposed procedure requires only one iteration for all the HC problems solved in this section. This last result confirms that the proposed solution based on sensitivities fits the bounds of the problem with high accuracy.

6. Conclusions

This work presents a novel methodology for assessing hosting capacity in unbalanced low-voltage networks, applicable to both distributed generation and demand integration. The proposed approach formulates the optimization problem based on a detailed network model and incorporates sensitivity analysis to construct a convex approximation. This simplifies the computational process while preserving accuracy and ensuring convergence. Results from tests conducted on real-world networks demonstrate that the methodology significantly improves computational efficiency and consistently yields optimal solutions that respect, without exceeding, the defined operational limits. In addition, these results demonstrate that the tool is well suited to quickly calculate the network hosting capacity, both for generation and demand, in different scenarios, allowing the implementation of this type of algorithm in planning tasks.

Thanks to the good performance of the tool, future work is aimed at its adaptation for the calculation of dynamic and not only static hosting capacity limits, commonly known as operating envelopes.

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Appendix

Equations (A-1) and (A-2) detail the formulation of (4) for all four phases (a, b, c and neutral wire) of bus i . The matrix $[\mathbf{U}_8]$ denotes the identity matrix of dimension 8×8 . For a more detailed explanation, reader is referred to [15].

$$\sum_{j=1}^N \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} G_{ij}^{aa} & -B_{ij}^{aa} & G_{ij}^{ab} & -B_{ij}^{ab} & G_{ij}^{ac} & -B_{ij}^{ac} & G_{ij}^{an} & -B_{ij}^{an} \\ B_{ij}^{aa} & G_{ij}^{aa} & B_{ij}^{ab} & G_{ij}^{ab} & B_{ij}^{ac} & G_{ij}^{ac} & B_{ij}^{an} & G_{ij}^{an} \\ \hline G_{ij}^{ba} & -B_{ij}^{ba} & G_{ij}^{bb} & -B_{ij}^{bb} & G_{ij}^{bc} & -B_{ij}^{bc} & G_{ij}^{bn} & -B_{ij}^{bn} \\ B_{ij}^{ba} & G_{ij}^{ba} & B_{ij}^{bb} & G_{ij}^{bb} & B_{ij}^{bc} & G_{ij}^{bc} & B_{ij}^{bn} & G_{ij}^{bn} \\ \hline G_{ij}^{ca} & -B_{ij}^{ca} & G_{ij}^{cb} & -B_{ij}^{cb} & G_{ij}^{cc} & -B_{ij}^{cc} & G_{ij}^{cn} & -B_{ij}^{cn} \\ B_{ij}^{ca} & G_{ij}^{ca} & B_{ij}^{cb} & G_{ij}^{cb} & B_{ij}^{cc} & G_{ij}^{cc} & B_{ij}^{cn} & G_{ij}^{cn} \\ \hline G_{ij}^{na} & -B_{ij}^{na} & G_{ij}^{nb} & -B_{ij}^{nb} & G_{ij}^{nc} & -B_{ij}^{nc} & G_{ij}^{nn} & -B_{ij}^{nn} \\ B_{ij}^{na} & G_{ij}^{na} & B_{ij}^{nb} & G_{ij}^{nb} & B_{ij}^{nc} & G_{ij}^{nc} & B_{ij}^{nn} & G_{ij}^{nn} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{Y}_{ij}} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \Delta e_j^a \\ \Delta f_j^a \\ \hline \Delta e_j^b \\ \Delta f_j^b \\ \hline \Delta e_j^c \\ \Delta f_j^c \\ \hline \Delta e_j^n \\ \Delta f_j^n \end{bmatrix}}_{\Delta \mathbf{V}_j} \\
- [\mathbf{U}_8] \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \Delta c_i^a \\ \Delta d_i^a \\ \hline \Delta c_i^b \\ \Delta d_i^b \\ \hline \Delta c_i^c \\ \Delta d_i^c \\ \hline \Delta c_i^n \\ \Delta d_i^n \end{bmatrix}}_{\Delta \mathbf{I}_i} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \hline 0 \\ 0 \\ \hline 0 \\ 0 \\ \hline 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A-1})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} c_i^a|_0 & d_i^a|_0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -c_i^a|_0 & -d_i^a|_0 \\ -d_i^a|_0 & c_i^a|_0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & d_i^a|_0 & -c_i^a|_0 \\ \hline 0 & 0 & c_i^b|_0 & d_i^b|_0 & 0 & 0 & -c_i^b|_0 & -d_i^b|_0 \\ 0 & 0 & -d_i^b|_0 & c_i^b|_0 & 0 & 0 & d_i^b|_0 & -c_i^b|_0 \\ \hline 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_i^c|_0 & d_i^c|_0 & -c_i^c|_0 & -d_i^c|_0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -d_i^c|_0 & c_i^c|_0 & d_i^c|_0 & -c_i^c|_0 \\ \hline 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{DI}_i|_0} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \Delta e_i^a \\ \Delta f_i^a \\ \hline \Delta e_i^b \\ \Delta f_i^b \\ \hline \Delta e_i^c \\ \Delta f_i^c \\ \hline \Delta e_i^n \\ \Delta f_i^n \end{bmatrix}}_{\Delta \mathbf{V}_j} \\
+ & \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \hat{e}_i^a|_0 & \hat{f}_i^a|_0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \hat{f}_i^a|_0 & -\hat{e}_i^a|_0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \hline 0 & 0 & \hat{e}_i^b|_0 & \hat{f}_i^b|_0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \hat{f}_i^b|_0 & -\hat{e}_i^b|_0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \hline 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \hat{e}_i^c|_0 & \hat{f}_i^c|_0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \hat{f}_i^c|_0 & -\hat{e}_i^c|_0 & 0 & 0 \\ \hline 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{DV}_i|_0} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \Delta c_i^a \\ \Delta d_i^a \\ \hline \Delta c_i^b \\ \Delta d_i^b \\ \hline \Delta c_i^c \\ \Delta d_i^c \\ \hline \Delta c_i^n \\ \Delta d_i^n \end{bmatrix}}_{\Delta \mathbf{I}_i} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \Delta P_i^a \\ \Delta Q_i^a \\ \hline \Delta P_i^b \\ \Delta Q_i^b \\ \hline \Delta P_i^c \\ \Delta Q_i^c \\ \hline 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}}_{\Delta \mathbf{S}_i} \\
& \tag{A-2}
\end{aligned}$$

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